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Title: Comparing the monetary value of health and well-being

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Objective

Broader quality of life measures aiming to assess overall well-being rather than mere health effects, recently gained relevance in health technology assessment. To be able to use these measurements in a cost-effectiveness framework, an assessment of the monetary value for broader quality of life is needed. Therefore, the aim of this analysis is to estimate the monetary value of broader quality of life gains, including a direct comparison to the monetary value of health gains.

Methods

This study applies the well-being valuation method to health and broader quality of life gains using a cross sectional, representative sample of 1,373 UK citizens aged 18 to 65, who completed an online survey in February 2018. Individual's subjective well-being, proxied by Cantril's ladder, is regressed on income, health and broader quality of life, which were assessed by EQ5D and ICECAP-A. The calculated coefficients of income and EQ-5D or ICECAP-A are then utilized to calculate the marginal rate of substitution – the percentage change in income necessary to maintain the same level of subjective well-being if EQ-5D or ICECAP-A would change by a certain amount. Based on average income and EQ-5D/ICECAP-A values, a monetary value for health and broader quality of life gains is calculated. Multiple extrapolations, based on varying assumptions, are conducted to calculate the corresponding implied values of a QALY or a well-being adjusted life year.

Results

In the lower case estimation, assuming diminishing marginal utility of health and well-being and using the weighted index values with a hypothetical change of one unit in EQ5D and ICECAP-A, the implied monetary value of a QALY is € 10,213 (SE € 2,584) and € 34,121 (SE € 2,445) for a well-being adjusted life year. The calculations were repeated alternating the following assumptions and input parameters: Using sum scores instead of weighted index values, imposing an incremental change instead of a one unit change, assuming linear marginal utility for health and well-being gains and inserting the different levels of EQ5D and ICECAP-A in separate regressions before extrapolating. This lead to varying results with an upper bound of the implied values of QALY and well-being adjusted life year of € 198,357 (SD € 42,750) and € 665,916 (SD € 170,550).

Discussion

The values of health are similar to those found using different methods, while the relative weight of well-being to health gains is consistently higher. Similar to studies estimating the WTP per QALY, the results of the well-being method vary considerably depending on the chosen set of assumptions. Therefore, exploring and discussing the most appropriate set of assumption is of paramount importance.